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“WALK AND WORK: A TEACHER’S VILLANELLE”

Walk and work, throughout the day
Prompt a well where wisdom flows
'Tis a noble fate, with a meager pay

Candles of knowledge, burn you may
Drive ignorance from the meadows
Walk and work, throughout the day

Explore the realms of uncertainty
To discover what nobody knows
'Tis a noble fate, with a meager pay

Prepare for the dark to break away
To see the poor young mind grows
Walk and work, throughout the day

Little footsteps repress the hallway
Eager for an intellectual discourse
'Tis a noble fate, with a meager pay

Indeed, lead and teach with dignity
Unleash the mind, bless the hallows
Walk and work, throughout the day
'Tis a noble fate, with a meager pay